

How Should Business Schools Adapt to the AI Era?

**Global Entrepreneurship Week
Postgraduate Hackathon**

Humber | CBS | University of Salford | GEA

**Discussion: A Framework for Institutional AI
Transition Readiness**

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From Inspiration to Framework

You just saw:

Global innovation
energy

Fast-changing
expectations

Emerging AI-
driven realities

Now: How do we translate that into
business school strategy?

Declaration on the Usage of AI in the Research

What I used	What I didn't use		
<p>✓ Analytical AI</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Deterministic scoring• Temperature = 0• Rubric-constrained• 100% reproducible	<p>✗ Generative AI</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• No AI-written text• No AI interpretation• No AI conclusions• Prevents Hallucinations		
<p>✓ AI as Instrument</p> <table border="0"><tr><td data-bbox="63 905 764 1178"><p>Custom R scripts</p><ul style="list-style-type: none">• dplyr for data manipulation• ggplot2 for visualization• Reproducible markdown reports• Free and open source</td><td data-bbox="810 905 1567 1235"><p>Python Chatbots</p><ul style="list-style-type: none">• BeautifulSoup for web scraping• PyMuPDF for PDF analysis• OpenAI for NLP/LLM text evaluation• Custom rubric scoring system• Deterministic, reproducible analysis</td></tr></table>	<p>Custom R scripts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• dplyr for data manipulation• ggplot2 for visualization• Reproducible markdown reports• Free and open source	<p>Python Chatbots</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• BeautifulSoup for web scraping• PyMuPDF for PDF analysis• OpenAI for NLP/LLM text evaluation• Custom rubric scoring system• Deterministic, reproducible analysis	<p>✗ Agentic AI</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• No unsupervised machine learning• No autonomous decisions• No black-box processes
<p>Custom R scripts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• dplyr for data manipulation• ggplot2 for visualization• Reproducible markdown reports• Free and open source	<p>Python Chatbots</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• BeautifulSoup for web scraping• PyMuPDF for PDF analysis• OpenAI for NLP/LLM text evaluation• Custom rubric scoring system• Deterministic, reproducible analysis		

The Big Question

**How ready are our colleges and business schools for the transition into the AI era?
Can you provide quantifiable evidence?**

Not just to teach AI, but to embrace and operate at the speed of AI.

Traditional Rigor Meets Exponential Disruption

TRADITIONAL ACADEMIC MODEL

Long approval process
Multi-year curriculum cycles
Strong but rigid QA

AI-DRIVEN REALITY

Rapid tool evolution
Generative & Agentic
Real-time adaptation

**The new does not need to replace the old,
and the old does not have to fear the new.**

Pairing Traditional and New Methods

Traditional Methodologies	AI Innovation	Outcomes
Agile Extreme Programming (XP)	ChatGPT Python Chatbot Writing	Generative AI to Write Codes ChatGPT as Paired Programmer
HTML Website Analysis	Python with BeautifulSoup Library	Natural Language Programming (NLP) Information Scraping of HTML sites
PDF Website Analysis	Python with PyMuPDF Library (fitz)	Natural Language Programming (NLP) Information Scraping of PDF sites
Rubrics-based Analysis	OpenAI Snippet Authoring	Large Language Modelling (LLM) Deterministic AI Report Writing
R Data Science Language	Python Chatbots Driving Automation	Public Dataset Analysis and Visualization (Plotting)at Scale
Lean Six Sigma Gage R&R, Monte Carlo	Python Chatbots Driving Automation	Quality Assurance, Data Validation and Large Sample Simulation

Research Methodology: Conceptual Framework

Rank	Institution	Avg. Final Governance Score	Sigma Tier
1	Harvard University	44.96	6 σ
2	University of Toronto	43.52	5 σ
3	Carnegie Mellon University	39.50	4 σ
4	University of California, Berkeley	37.26	5 σ
5	University of Oxford	36.38	4 σ
6	ETH Zurich	36.04	6 σ
7	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	34.86	6 σ
8	National University of Singapore	33.96	6 σ
9	Nanyang Technological University	32.80	3 σ
10	Hong Kong University of Science & Technology	31.50	3 σ

Findings: Establishing a Global Governance Benchmark

- QS World Top 10 AI Universities used as the prototype for governance evaluation.
- Benchmark defined world-class standards for AI policy maturity, transparency, and strategic direction.
- Governance weighting: 50% of AI Transition Readiness Index (TRI).
- Serves as reference point for Ontario’s comparative positioning.

Sigma Tier shows repeatable and reproducible accuracy using Six Sigma measuring standards.

Rank	Institution	Average Governance Score	DPMO	Sigma Tier
1	Harvard	44.96	0	6σ
2	Toronto	43.52	12	5σ
3	Sheridan	41.1	110	5σ
4	Fanshawe	39.52	240	4σ
5	Carnegie Mellon	39.5	476	4σ
6	UC Berkeley	37.26	14	5σ
7	Conestoga	36.72	199	5σ
8	Oxford	36.38	5,583	4σ
9	Algonquin	36.28	1,561	4σ
10	ETH Zurich	36.04	0	6σ
11	Humber	35.86	23,441	3σ
12	Centennial	34.94	9,869	3σ
13	Seneca	34.86	0	6σ
14	MIT	34.86	0	6σ
15	NUS	33.96	0	6σ
16	Durham	33.84	368	4σ
17	Niagara	33.58	20,439	3σ
18	Loyalist	33.26	0	6σ
19	George Brown	32.86	0	6σ
20	Nanyang Technological University	32.8	50,031	3σ
21	Georgina	31.72	191	5σ

Findings: Ontario's Global Governance Leaders

- Applying identical criteria, two Ontario colleges—Sheridan and Fanshawe—ranked 3rd and 4th globally in Governance, trailing only Harvard and U of T.
- Addresses RQ1 (Governance readiness) and RQ3 (Benchmarking against global leaders).
- Demonstrates that Ontario institutions can match or exceed world-class governance standards.

Quality Assurance and Methodological Integrity

Governance at 50% Weight

Attribute & Normalized Index	Weight (%)	Coll. A	Norm. A	Coll. B	Norm. B
G	50	45	56.25	35	43.75
P	12.5	8	14.29	6	10.71
L	12.5	8	14.29	6	10.71
A	12.5	8	14.29	6	10.71
C	12.5	8	14.29	6	10.71
TR _{raw}	100	77		59	
TR _{norm}	100		113.39		86.61

Midpoint normalization applied for institutional equity regardless of size

Six Sigma framework ensured reproducibility and repeatability of results.

IMF AML/CFT model ensured fair and unbiased data collection.

$$\text{Normalized Value} = \frac{\text{Raw Score} \times 100}{(\text{Provincial Maximum} + \text{Provincial Minimum})/2}$$

Rank	Institution	TRI (G) 50%	TRI (PLAC) 50%	Sub- total	Midpoint Normalized	TRI Score (Baseline =100)
1	Seneca	53.97	51.11	105.08	193.71	171.22
2	Algonquin	55.98	43.88	99.86	184.09	162.71
3	Conestoga	56.79	40.81	97.60	179.92	159.03
4	Loyalist	51.49	44.87	96.36	177.64	157.01
5	Centennial	54.06	41.66	95.72	176.46	155.97
6	George Brown	50.84	44.18	95.02	175.17	154.83
7	Sheridan	63.63	27.70	91.33	168.37	148.81
8	Durham	52.33	38.43	90.76	167.31	147.88
9	Humber	55.52	32.93	88.45	163.06	144.12
10	Fanshawe	61.19	24.84	86.03	158.60	140.18
11	Georgian	49.11	23.47	72.58	133.80	118.26
12	Cambrian	47.31	21.78	69.09	127.37	112.58
–	Ontario Average	–	–	61.48	113.14	100.00
13	Niagara	51.93	9.55	61.48	113.34	100.18
14	St. Clair	39.85	20.75	60.60	111.72	98.74
15	Canadore	40.75	16.85	57.60	106.18	93.85
16	Lambton	0.00	47.20	47.20	87.01	76.91
17	Sault	0.00	32.05	32.05	59.08	52.22
18	Mohawk	0.00	31.37	31.37	57.83	51.11
19	La Cité	0.00	26.58	26.58	49.00	43.31
20	Confederation	15.23	10.44	25.67	47.32	41.83
21	Fleming	0.00	19.32	19.32	35.62	31.48
22	Northern	0.00	13.31	13.31	24.54	21.69
23	St. Lawrence	0.00	6.46	6.46	11.91	10.53
24	Boreal	0.00	3.41	3.41	6.29	5.56

TRI

Findings: Ranked Normalized TRI – Apples-to-Apples Comparison

- Corrected earlier misalignments and applied consistent scaling logic to all subcomponents.
- Maintained intended weighting influence for each variable.
- Produced statistically sound, normalized 100-point scale.

Discussion: Percentage of AI Transitional Readiness (Will vs. Way)

Discussion: When High Will Meets Variable Way

- High Governance (“Will”) often boosts rankings due to its 50% TRI weight.
- Some high-Governance colleges underperformed when **Programs, Learners, SMA, and Classification** (the “Way”) were factored in.
- Reveals operational capacity gaps despite strong governance intent.
- Answers **RQ2** (Operational readiness).

Will–Way scattered quadrant plot showing shifts in rankings after operational factors added.

AI Training Participation: Ontario Colleges vs National Landscape

Two Jump-Start AI Tips

1. AI is more than GenAI
(Analytic, Deterministic, Agentic,
etc.) Learn Prompt Engineering!

2. Temperature = 0 to reduce
hallucinations

What This Means for Business Schools

Agile curriculum cycles

AI as partner

Blend AI + traditional validation

Build AI literacy

Use G-PLAC for strategy

If You Want to Build on This Work...

Scan the QR code to access the dissertation DOI

DOI:

[10.5281/zenodo.16990734](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16990734)

